

MONEY, INCOME, AND CAUSALITY: THE BANGLADESH EXPERIENCE

MD. NISAR AHMED SHAMS* MUHAMMAD MOSADDEK HOSSAIN**
AND MD. MAHMUDUL HASSAN***

ABSTRACT

This paper seeks to examine the causal relationship between money and income in Bangladesh economy covering the period 1972/73 to 2007/08. The cointegration analysis indicates a long-run relationship between money and income. The error correction framework suggests a one-way causation from money to income in the short-run as well as in the long-run implying a relatively active role for money in influencing economic activities in Bangladesh.

I. Introduction

The causal relationship between Money and Income is of immense importance in designing and implementing monetary policy. Monetarists hold the view that money has an active role in income generation. Therefore, the direction of causation runs from money to income without any feedback. On the contrary, Keynesians reject the Monetarists view that changes in income are solely caused by changes in money supply. Rather they hold that changes in income leads to changes in money supply implying a unidirectional causality from income to money.

The determination of the direction of causation between money and income is crucial for implementing policies aimed at economic growth and development. Sims (1972) sets off the empirical study on money-income relationship based on the Granger Causality test. Using post-war quarterly data for U.S. in the bivariate framework, Sims findings was in line with the view of the monetarists; i.e. unidirectional causality running from money to income. Barth and Bennett (1974) applied the test procedure as adopted by Sims in case of Canadian data for the period 1957 to 1972. The study found bidirectional causality between money and income. Williams et al. (1976) employing a similar approach found evidence of unidirectional causality from income to money in case of U.K. Investigating the causal relationship between income and monetary aggregates in U.S. for the period January 1959 to December 2002, Hill (2007) identified linear causation from money to income.

* Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh.

** Lecturer, Department of Economics, School of Social Science, Comilla University, Kotbari, Comilla- 3503, Bangladesh.

*** Graduate Student, Department of Economics, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh.

Replicating Sims test in case of Pakistan, Hussain (1991) found unidirectional causality running from broad money to income. However, the findings reversed in case of narrow money. A unidirectional causality from income to narrow money is identified which is similar to the conclusion made by Williams et al. (1976). Later, Abbas and Husain (2006) found unidirectional causality running from income to money for Pakistan which was based on the annual data set for the period FY 1959-60 to 2003-04. In a recent study, Yadav (2008) investigated the causality and long-run relationship between money, and income in India. The study revealed a set of varied results. Causality is found to be unidirectional from real GNP to real money supply and bidirectional from nominal income to nominal money supply during 1950-51 to 2006-07.

The objective of this paper is to empirically test whether changes in money supply leads to changes in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) without any feedback between both the variables in Bangladesh economy. The study concentrates on cointegration and error correction models to look into the bivariate causal relationship by taking care of the stochastic properties of the variables used. If the variables are nonstationary, the regression results would be 'spurious'. Thus it is necessary to check for stationarity of the variables. If the variables are stationary as well cointegrated, we can arrive at a conclusion that the variables have a long-run relationship between them. The direction of causation between money supply and GDP is identified with the help of error correction model.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the methodology which tests the stochastic properties of the variables and their inter-relationship. Section III provides the data sources and empirical results. The last section contains the conclusions of the study.

II. Methodology

The formal investigation starts by checking the stochastic properties of the variables used in the analysis. It is very important to ensure that the variables are stationary of the same order before proceeding to other estimations. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test (Dickey and Fuller, 1981) with a time trend is used for detecting a unit root in the series for Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Narrow Money (M_1) and Broad Money (M_2). The following equation is used in conducting the ADF test:

$$\Delta Y_t = b_0 + b_1 t + b_2 Y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \zeta_j \Delta Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad \text{-----} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), Δ is the first difference operator and ε_t is the white noise error term. The null hypothesis that Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Narrow Money (M_1) and Broad Money (M_2) are nonstationary time series is rejected if b_2 is less than zero and statistically significant. The ADF test is carried out by replacing Y_t with GDP_t , M_{1t} and M_{2t} in equation (1).

Next, we apply the Engle-Granger cointegration test to examine the long-run relations among variables. Two or more variables are cointegrated if they are integrated of the same order. The first step consists in identifying the order of integration of the variables included in the model. The second step requires the estimation of the cointegration regression using variables having the same order of integration. The following cointegration equations are estimated:

$$X_t = \alpha + \beta Y_t + u_t \quad \text{-----} \quad (2)$$

$$Y_t = \gamma + \delta X_t + u'_t \quad \text{-----} \quad (3)$$

X and Y will be cointegrated if they are integrated of the same order i.e., $I(d)$ and the residuals from the cointegration equations (u_t and u'_t) are integrated of order less than d . For example, GDP_t and M_{1t} will be cointegrated if the residuals in the regression of GDP_t on M_{1t} (and vice versa) is $I(0)$ provided that $GDP_t \sim I(1)$ and $M_{1t} \sim I(1)$.

If cointegration exists between two variables, then standard Granger causality cannot be used as it ignores the possible long-run relationship. Vector error correction will be used to test for Granger causality direction. In spite of a long-run relationship between the variables, there may be disequilibrium in the short run. An error correction model (ECM) merges the long-run relationship with the short-run dynamics of the model in the presence of cointegrated variables. This approach consists in estimating the first difference of both the dependent and explanatory variables. According to Engle and Granger (1987), when X_t and Y_t are found to be cointegrated, the specification of ECM can be expressed as:

$$\Delta X_t = \lambda_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \theta_i \Delta X_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \xi_j \Delta Y_{t-j} + \rho_1 \mu_{t-1} + v_t \quad \text{-----} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta Y_t = \gamma_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \psi_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \zeta_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \rho_2 \eta_{t-1} + v_t \quad \text{-----} \quad (5)$$

where Δ is the first difference operator, μ_{t-1} and η_{t-1} are the error correction terms which represents the lagged residuals from the cointegrating equations, n and m are the number of lag lengths chosen by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and v_t and v_t are the disturbance terms. The error correction terms μ_{t-1} and η_{t-1} measures the deviations of the series from the long-run equilibrium relations. In the above two equations, the series X_t and Y_t are cointegrated when at least one of the coefficients ρ_1 and ρ_2 is not zero. In addition, short-run dynamics between X_t and Y_t are characterized by the coefficients ξ_j 's and ζ_j 's. If ξ_j 's are not all zero, movements in Y_t will cause X_t in the short-run. On the other hand, if ζ_j 's are not all zero, movements in X_t will lead to Y_t in the short-run. The error correction mechanism is carried out by replacing X_t with GDP_t , Y_t with M_{1t} and M_{2t} respectively in equations (4) and (5).

III. Data and Empirical Results

The analysis in this study is based on annual data covering the period from 1972/73 to 2007/08. Data on Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Narrow Money (M_1) which consists of currency outside banks, demand deposits as well as deposits with Bangladesh Bank other than deposit money banks and (M_2) which includes time deposits along with narrow money, have been obtained from various publication of Economic Trends, published by the Bangladesh Bank¹. Econometric estimations have been done by using STATA 9.1.

Table 1: Unit Root Test with ADF for the period 1972/73 to 2007/08

Variables	ADF		ADF	
	C	First Difference	C, T	First Difference
GDP	-2.614(2)	-2.622(2)*	-2.577(2)	-3.622(2)**
M_1	-2.044(1)	-6.497(1)***	-3.121(1)	-3.826(1)**
M_2	-2.621(1)	-4.562(1)***	-3.218(1)	-4.317(1)***

Notes: i) C = constant term included in the unit root test, C,T = constant and trend term included in unit root test; ii) Figures within parentheses indicate lag lengths chosen by the Akaike information criterion (AIC); iii) ***, ** and * denote rejection of the null hypothesis of unit root at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.

Results of the unit-root tests are reported in Table-1. The results indicate that at the levels GDP, M_1 and M_2 are nonstationary. Therefore to achieve stationarity the variables must be first-differenced. The ADF statistics are only significant only for the first-differenced series. Thus, GDP, M_1 and M_2 all appear to be $I(1)$.

Table 2: Unit Root Rest for the Residuals 'u_t'

With M_1 Definition of Money		With M_2 Definition of Money	
Cointegrating Regressions	ADF	Cointegrating Regressions	ADF
$GDP_t = 74351.09 + 4.31 M_{1t}$	-2.619(1)*	$GDP_t = 31757.28 + 2.24 M_{2t}$	-2.975(1)*
$M_{1t} = 1948.84 + 0.09 GDP_t$	-4.278(1)***	$M_{2t} = -12255.01 + 0.43 GDP_t$	-3.173(1)**

Notes: i) Figures within parentheses indicate lag lengths chosen by the Akaike information criterion (AIC); ii) ***, ** and * denote rejection of the null hypothesis of unit root at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.

The ADF statistics for the cointegration tests are presented in Table-2. The residuals of the cointegrating regressions are stationary indicating that deviations between GDP and M_1 as well as M_2 settle together in the long-run. Thus, there seems to exist a long-run relationship between GDP and money supply (M_1 and M_2) which will not lead to any 'spurious regression'.

¹ GDP, M_1 and M_2 are expressed in terms of Taka (domestic currency of Bangladesh) in Crores. 1 Crore = 10 Million.

After establishing a long-run relationship between money and income, the next is to identify which variable causes the other and provides the short-run dynamics towards long-run equilibrium.

Table-3: Error Correction Model

With M ₁ Definition of Money			With M ₂ Definition of Money		
Explanatory Variables	Dependent Variables		Explanatory Variables	Dependent Variables	
	ΔGDP_t	ΔM_{1t}		ΔGDP_t	ΔM_{2t}
Constant	747.91(0.53)	77.31(0.02)	Constant	833.93(0.43)	-1436.36(-0.35)
EC Term	-0.21(-4.65)***	0.04(0.69)	EC Term	-0.09(-1.76)*	0.05(0.41)
ΔGDP_{t-1}	0.11(1.55)	0.31(0.35)	ΔGDP_{t-1}	0.19(1.06)	0.01(0.24)
$\Delta M_{1(t-1)}$	0.97(7.15)***	0.17(0.967)	ΔGDP_{t-2}	0.08(0.04)	0.07(1.06)
			$\Delta M_{2(t-1)}$	-0.42(-1.88)*	0.05(0.24)
			$\Delta M_{2(t-2)}$	-0.37(-3.28)**	-0.43(-0.55)

Notes: i) Figures in parenthesis are z-statistics; ii) The optimal lag length has been considered to be 2 (with M₁ definition of Money) and 3 (with M₂ definition of Money) according to the Akaike information criterion (AIC); iii) ***, ** and * indicate significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively; iv) Figures corresponding to the EC term are the coefficients of the error correction terms in the relevant equations.

The estimated coefficients of the error correction term (long-run effects) and the lagged values of the two series (short-run effects) are presented in Table-3. The results show the existence of significant relationship between GDP and narrow money as well as broad money. The estimated coefficient of the error correction term is significant at the 1 percent level from M₁ to GDP while it is significant at the 10 percent level from M₂ to GDP. Besides, movements in M₁ and M₂ will lead to cause GDP in the short-run. Unidirectional causality between money and income is found both in the short-run and in the long-run. It runs from money to income without any feedback effect.

IV. Conclusions

The purpose of this paper has been to investigate the causal relationship between money and income in Bangladesh economy. A unidirectional causality from money to income is found to exist both in the short-run as well as in the long-run supporting the Monetarist view that money plays a major role in income generation.

The policy implication that arises from this analysis suggests that monetary policy plays a major role in determining the level of output in Bangladesh. An expansionary monetary policy increases money supply which leads to a fall in interest rate. With lower interest rates, aggregate expenditures on investment and interest sensitive consumption goods usually increase, causing GDP to rise. Thus, expansionary monetary policy may increase the level of GDP by increasing aggregate demand. However, a given increase in the quantity of money always leads to a proportional increase in the price level. As a result output increase at a higher price leading to inflation. The monetary authorities should conduct monetary policy in such a way that keeps the growth rate of the money

supply fixed at a rate that is equal to the growth rate of the economy over time in order to contain persistent periods of inflation. Such a policy should serve to accommodate increases in GDP without causing inflation.

REFERENCES

- Barth, J. R., and J. T. Bennett, 1974, "The Role of Money in the Canadian Economy: An Empirical Test", *Canadian Journal of Economics*, Vol. 7, pp. 306–311.
- Dickey, D. A. and W. A. Fuller, 1979, "Distribution of the Estimators for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root", *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, Vol. 74, pp. 427-431.
- Dickey, D. A. and W. A. Fuller, 1981, "Likelihood Ratio Statistics for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root", *Econometrica*, Vol. 49, pp.1057-1072.
- Enders, W., 1995, *Applied Time Series Econometrics*, John Wiley and Sons Inc. New York.
- Engle, R. F. and C. W. Granger, 1987, "Co-integration and Error Correction: Representation, Estimation and Testing", *Econometrica*, Vol. 55, pp. 251-276.
- Granger, C.W.J., 1969, "Investigating Causal Relations by Econometric Models and Cross-spectral Methods", *Econometrica*, Vol. 37, pp. 424-436.
- Greene, W. H., 2003, *Econometric Analysis*, Pearson Education, Inc., New Jersey.
- Gujarati, D. N., 2003, *Basic Econometrics*, McGraw Hill, New York.
- Hill, J., 2007, "Efficient tests of long-run causation in Trivariate VAR processes with a rolling window study of the money-income relationship", *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, Vol. 22, pp. 747–765.
- Husain, F. and K. Abbas, 2000, "Money, Income, Prices, and Causality in Pakistan: A Trivariate Analysis", Research Report No. 178, Pakistan Institute of Development Economics (PIDE).
- Hussain, M., 1991, "Money, Income, and Causality: Some Evidence from Pakistan", *The Pakistan Development Review*, Vol. 30, No. 4, pp. 907-918.
- Sims, C., 1972, "Money, Income, and Causality", *American Economic Review*, Vol. 62, pp. 540–552.
- Williams, D., C. A. E. Goodhart, and D. H. Gowland, 1976, "Money, Income, and Causality: The U.K. Experience", *American Economic Review*, Vol. 66, No. 3, pp. 417–423.
- Yadav, I. S., 2008, "Co-integration, Causality, Money and Income in India", Department of Economics, University of Hyderabad, A.P., Retrieved on 18 December, 2009.
- http://www.igidr.ac.in/~money/mfc_10/Indershekar%20Yadav_money_supply.pdf